

Community Activation: What is it?

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Introduction

Community Activation is a community building approach that is used by organizations and groups to develop their place-based and online communities based on empowerment principles. This working paper provides an overview of Community Activation by defining what it is, why it is used, and how to use it. The Community Activation framework was developed by Middle Path EcoSolutions (Middle Path).

What is Community Activation?

"Community" is defined here as a group of people who have come together to collaborate to reach a shared goal. Community Activation is an approach that helps communities develop in empowered and people-centered ways, so they can self-mobilize, self-organize, and self-determine the best ways to reach their goals.

Community Activation consists of 4 different levels: Community Outreach, Community Engagement, Community Building, and Community Mobilization (see below). Each level is implemented based on the context and needs of the community. While community mobilization is the pinnacle of a Community Activation process, it may not be the right fit for the goals of a community. Instead, a community may seek to implement only the lower stages of Community Activation.

How is Community Activation different from other forms of community development? Community Activation relies on strong empowerment principles that show up in every dimension of the community organizing, management, and participation. In contrast, most conventional community development is conducted through a top-down approach, such as by emphasizing the community manager as the main decision-maker and enabler for making things happen in a community. For

Note: This white paper is based on content originally developed on the website <https://middlepatheco.com/>, which was founded in 2016.

example, a community manager may facilitate all of the community meetings and interactions between members.

The Community Activation process, on the other hand, focuses on creating organizational structures that decentralize management, and supports an environment of processes and attitudes that help empower community members. Community managers (or we prefer the term "community stewards") seek to "lead from behind"¹ by pushing themselves out of the center, and creating more space for community members to engage and lead.

Why use Community Activation?

Here are some ways that a Community Activation approach benefits an organization or project:

- Increases an organization's alignment with members' needs and expectations
- Maintains the long-term relevance of an organization
- Increases an organization's efficiency, such as by leveraging volunteer contributions
- Discovers new applications of an organization's services
- Increases an organization's benefit to society
- Reduces the risk of burnout of community organizers, managers, and leaders

How to use Community Activation?

Community Activation consists of 4 different levels (Figure 1), and each contains different tools and emphases. Figuring out which level to use in your community, depends on its context and the readiness of your community members². As your community evolves or changes, you may find that you can move between different levels of Community Activation. It may even make sense to use different levels in your community at the same time, especially if you have a mixture of both new and existing programs or activities. In the Community Activation pyramid in Figure 1, the levels are

¹ Scharmer, C. O. (2009). *Theory U: Learning from the future as it emerges*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.

² The connection between context and approach is similar to how participatory approaches are used in rural development, as described in the paper by Pretty, J. (1995) [Participatory learning for sustainable agriculture](#), *World Development*, 23 (8), 1247–1263.

arranged by what is most broadly used, mostly because the higher levels require more specific contexts to be applicable.

1. Community Outreach

Community Outreach is the very first step of any prospective community. It is a stage when the earliest members are seeking to identify the best audiences for the community and trying to understand why these audiences might be interested in being a part of the community (i.e., identifying the value propositions for different audiences). This will also be a time that a community is learning which outreach mechanisms work best with each audience, and how best to connect with them.

Some questions a community might be addressing during Community Outreach:

- Who are my audiences?
- How do I reach them?
- Why might different audiences be interested in being a part of our community?
- How do we communicate our community mission?

2. Community Engagement

Community Engagement is the development of mutually beneficial relationships between an organization and target external groups. This step consists of mostly gathering and convening people together. Community Engagement is made possible once a community has identified specific audiences for the community and ways to reach out to them, and has at least one mechanism to bring them on board. Some examples of mechanisms are signing up for a newsletter, following a social media page, or attending events. Community Engagement is the foundation of any community-based initiative, and is often where many communities find themselves stuck (i.e., “now that I've collected all of these people together, what do I do next?”). In this step, a community is often spending time encouraging and incentivizing people to join them, while fine tuning the value proposition that most resonates with the different audiences most aligned with the community mission.

Some questions a community might be addressing during Community Engagement:

- What activities should I be doing to engage my audiences?
- What does it mean for someone to be a member in our community?
- What kind of benefits can our community offer members?

- What is the scope of our community? (what does it do and not do)

3. Community Building

If you have gathered together a group of people around a common mission, and they are eager to work together, you now have the foundation for a community. In the Community Building stage, a community will focus on developing the organizational structures that support an environment of interactions, allowing community members to interact effectively and independently without much help or intervention by a community steward. Some examples of structures include: working groups, collaboration platforms--like a Slack workspace or Facebook group, and collaborative documents and files (like a Google folder). This is a very busy stage for a community, since they'll be working hard to create and develop new structures that support their collaborative activities.

Some questions a community might be addressing during Community Building:

- What activities do our members want to accomplish together?
- What infrastructure and processes do we need to help members connect and collaborate with each other independently?
- How can members be an active part of helping the community develop and function?

4. Community Mobilization

Community mobilization is the gold standard for empowered communities. Community mobilization is possible when community members feel able to make decisions, self-organize and take actions in a coordinated way on behalf of the community. In this level, you'll see an effective governance structure with changing diverse leadership, active and enthusiastic members, well-documented community processes, and a membership that understands what their mission is all about. A mobilized community is easiest to manage because there are many leaders and do-ers in the community, and things hum along like clockwork.

Some questions a community might be addressing during Community Mobilization:

- Are our community processes reflective of our values as a community?

- How can we ensure equitable participation and leadership in our community?
- What are ways that we can self-assess and improve our processes?
- What are some signs that our community mobilization is working?

Figure 1. Community Activation Growth Pyramid

Conclusion

A Community Activation is both a theoretical framework and an actionable approach to help communities develop in empowered ways that support their self-mobilization, self-organization, and self-determination. Although there are 4 different levels involved in Community Activation, a community may choose to implement only the lower levels, since each level is applicable depending on a community's specific context, needs, and goals. Community Activation has been implemented successfully by Middle Path among different organizations and emergent groups that seek to engage and develop their communities.